

SUBSTANCE USES, DEPRESSION, SOCIAL ANXIETY AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The current study aims to explore Substance use, Depression, Social Anxiety and Academic Achievement among University Students. The observation of substance use, Depression, Social Anxiety and educational Achievement is so essential in this cutting-edge era. The sample for the present study of 225 (95 male and 130 female) changed into decided on from exceptional universities the purposive sampling technique. A correlational research design and convenient sampling technique were to measure study variables. Adult, Academic Performance Rating Scale, depression and social anxiety scale used where to check substance use, and Drug Use Questionnaire (DAST 28) were applied. The observed findings suggest that a large tremendous courting among materials makes use of, melancholy, social tension among university students. Multiple linear regression and t-tests on sample analyses for inferential facts were additionally done to check the hypotheses. The findings confirmed a large sample uses drugs and faces mental health issues but a value of (-1.01) shows a small distinction between male and female substance use. Similarly, the t-value of -1.04 suggests a small distinction between male and female depression levels. The p-value of 0.298 showed that this distinction isn't statistically large. No distinction was found in depression ranges among male and female university students. The t-value of -1.43 represents a distinctly small distinction in social anxiety rankings among male and female students. The consequences suggest largely terrible courting among substance use and educational achievement among university students. Results additionally suggest depression and social anxiety are terribly correlated with academic achievements. Findings found that there are no large variations between male and female university students in phrases of substance use, depression, social anxiety and educational performance amongst university students. The consequences found that substance use of are slight tremendous large predictor of depression among university students. The study focuses on the significance of addressing substance use, melancholy, and social anxiety among students to enhance their academic overall performance and well-being.

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INTRODUCTION

The ancient backdrop of mankind has likewise been a heritage marked through continual drug use., as it should be directed, it had been a medical aid. Through the route of many years, the usage of illegal medicinal drugs has emerged as an uncommonly long way and extensive and has arrived. Numerous scientists have looked for the motive for continual drug use/addiction so compelling remedy and anticipation techniques may be laid out. Research has found that the difficulty comes from severe viewpoints: own circle of relatives' assets and individuals with a teen invest power with likewise affect his/her propensities. Companions will normally acquaint others with drug use. Another variable affecting continual drug use is the absence of records approximately the influences of the medication. (Cranford et al.). In the current study considerable delegate take a look at of youngsters to determine the diploma to which the presence of early-lifestyles emotional troubles is associated with we middle explicitly round substance trial and mistakes amongst kids for two reasons. One is early formative remedy or liquor trial and mistakes are a tremendous gamble element for destiny substance reliance. Second, we underscore substance trial and mistakes due to the fact that this behavior is to be had in adolescence, even though greater crucial substances use isn't. intended for occasion, a massive instance of 9 to seventeen years displayed that simply 1.2% of those kids` mishandled medicines or liquor. Subsequently, a in all likelihood sturdy exploration manner to address higher recognize the formative etiology of substance maltreatment in grown-ups is probably to 0 in on covariates and anticipated drivers of substance trial and mistakes in youth ((Andrews & Duncan, 1997). Depression stands a normal additionally stern mental syndrome that negatively affects the manner you're feeling, what you consider and the manner you react. Wretchedness generates hard conditions or doubtlessly a deficiency of enthusiasm in sports in that you as soon as excelled. Substance abuse and intellectual prosperity issues, for instance, horror and anxiety are solidly associated even though one does not be ensured to actually purpose the other

Regardless, materials like alcohol, that is a depressant, can increment weakness, influencing fixation, restraints, navigation, and reaction times. Liquor, gem methamphetamine, and narcotic use may activate nodding off running or in scholastic establishments. Liquor, pot, and tobacco are the maximum basically applied materials amongst university understudies but unlawful usage of various medicines along with energizers, stimulants, and narcotic anguish meds is popping from 37.4% to 39.1% (Substance Misuse and Psychological health Depression stands a normal additionally stern. yet illegal utilization of different medications including energizers, stimulants, and narcotic agony meds is turning out to be progressively normal the utilization of unlawful substances among youthful grown- ups expanded from 37.4% to 39.1%. The utilization of substances among college understudies is related with a bunch of adverse results including delinquency and below point midpoints, rape, and self-damaging way of behaving among others (Patterson, DeBaryshe, & Ramsey, 1990).

Social Phobia (anxiety) is portrayed by a drawn-out and overpowering feeling of dread toward social circumstances. A typical issue regularly starts around puberty. Social phobia is portrayed in the DSM-5

as a Stepped fear or uneasiness around something like one social situation in which the individual is introduced to possible assessment by others. Social anxiousness is visible as a predictor variable for precise people has low or traditional social anxiety tiers and others having excessive to outstandingly sure tiers. .This is moreover proper for humans with subclinical stages of social strain. In a large epidemiological evaluation amongst faculty that over forty-percentage of the respondents with social worry likewise had substance use jumbled. Young those who sense that they're suffering socially or are socially stressed is probably leaned to comply with peers, now no longer feeling sufficient, socially, to choose their personal course. Thusly, they could go with others in substance use looking to paintings on their monetary health and be vital for the buddy bunch (Lac& Luk 2018).

Academic success depicts scholastic outcomes that display the diploma to which an understudy has executed their getting to know objectives. .Substance use predominant region of electricity for has and social parts, like scholastic grades, participation, low confidence, withdrawn behavior, and lack of inspiration. Risk that usage is everyday Marijuana use negatively influences instructional performance (decrease GPA) quite greater than alcohol. There are numerous pathways prompting the special destructive results of substance use all through teenagers. (Gottfried & Kirksey, 2017). Henry calculated a polysubstance use score (the imply of factors to mirror tobacco, alcohol, and weed use), and noticed that it become in a fashionable feel related to much among college students whose grades lessened throughout 3 years of middle faculty, simple augmentations have been discovered with inside the polysubstance use (Henry, 2007) The study highlights a significant correlation between substance use, depression, and social anxiety among university students, with adverse implications for academic achievement. Addressing these interconnected factors through targeted interventions is crucial for promoting student well-being and academic success in higher education institutions.

THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework for this subject matter ought to draw upon diverse theories in psychology, which includes the cognitive-behavioral theory, which indicates that our thoughts, feelings, and behaviors are interconnected(Compas, et al., 2001) Other theories, which includes the social getting to know theory, can also be beneficial in expertise how college students study from their friends and the way social interactions can Additionally, the biopsychosocial version can be used to discover how biological, psychological, and social elements engage to steer substance use, depression, social anxiety, and educational success amongst university students. The conceptual framework examines how substance use, depression, and social anxiety among college students are influenced by various factors, including peer pressure, stress, individual psychological traits, past experiences, and cognitive biases, while academic success is impacted by motivation, study habits, and time management skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

In the current study correlational research was used to check the link between study variables. The goal

of correlational research designs is to examine the link between the variables while choosing participants who have some associations. This allowed for the identification and evaluation of their differences (Sekaran et al., 2003).

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was used to approach the university students. In current study 225 students participated (Male, 95 females, 130) from universities between the ages of 18 to 35. Thumb rule used to calculate the sample size. (Van Belle, 2011).

Procedure

In the current study 225 students were recruited from different universities National Textile University and Government College University Faisalabad. Both male and female students in the age range 18-35 were included in the study. To make certain moral suggestions are observed knowledgeable consent was won after candidates. Current research pursuits to research courting among substance use, depression, social tension and educational fulfilment amongst university students. Data accrued the use of a self-administered questionnaire that the questionnaire turned together with the degree of Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale -42 (Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995), Drug Use Questionnaire Skinner, (Skinner & Harvey,1982). Academic Performance Rating scale (Aafreen et al., 2018) was applied Demographic information on age, gender and education level was collected. Data were analyzed by using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and t-tests to summarize the demographic information and the distribution of scores in the substance use, depression, social anxiety and academic achievement measures.

RESULTS

Table 1: *Frequencies and Percentages of Demographic Variables of Study (N = 225)*

Variables	Category	F	%
Gender	Male	95	42.2
	Female	130	57.8
Age	19-26	154	68.4
	27-33	71	31.6
Education	BS	159	70.7
	MS	66	29.3
	Total	225	100.0

Note. F = Frequency, % = Percentage

The above table shows the demographic characteristics of the sample. The age ranges, and gender frequencies are 100%. In the sample of 225, there were 95 male and 130 female students with the age range of 22-30. Frequencies of ages 19-26 were 154 and 27-33 were 71.

Table 2: *Psychometric Properties of the Substance Uses, Depression, Social Anxiety and Academic Performance Scales (N=225)*

Scales	SD	M	Range	α	Skewness	Kurtosis
Substance Uses Scale	3.43	29.31	20-24	.62	1.78	4.81
Depression Scale	3.52	21.68	15-31	.68	.148	-.059
Social Anxiety Scale	5.66	23.95	15-38	.67	.555	-.299
Academic Performance Scale	4.50	21.96	12-30	.60	-.377	-.706

Table 2 shows the mean standard deviation, kurtosis, skewness and reliability of variables. The descriptive statistics is used to check the overall distribution of data across study variables.

Table 3: *Bivariate Correlation between Substance Use, Depression, Social Anxiety and Academic Achievement among University Students*

	Variables	1	2	3	4
1	Substance Use	-	.395**	.167*	-.178**
2	Depression	-	-	.460**	-.144*
3	Social Anxiety	-	-	-	-.147*
4	Academic Achievement				

Note. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$

The result depicted a significant positive relationship between substance use, depression, and social anxiety among university students. Results also show a significant negative relationship between substance use and academic achievement among university students. Results also show depression and social anxiety are negatively significantly correlated with academic achievement.

Table 4: *Mean Difference between Male and Female University Students in Terms Substance Uses, Depression, Social Anxiety and Academic Achievement among University Students*

	Male(n=95)		Female(n=130)		t	p	95% CI	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
Substance Uses	29.04	3.04	29.51	3.70	-1.01	.309	-1.38	.441
Depression	21.39	3.46	21.88	3.55	-1.04	.298	-1.43	.441
Social Anxiety	23.32	5.51	24.41	5.74	-1.43	.154	-2.59	.411
Academic Achievement	22.53	4.20	21.55	4.67	1.60	.110	-.220	2.16

Note. LL = Lower limit, UL = Upper limit

Table revealed that there no significant differences between male and female university students in terms of substance uses, depression, social anxiety and academic achievement. The t-value of -1.01 suggests a small difference between male and female substance use scores. The p-value of 0.309 indicates that this difference is not statistically significant at the conventional significance level. Therefore, based on this data, there is no strong evidence to conclude that there is a significant difference in substance use between male and female university students. Similarly, the t-value of -1.04 indicates a small difference between male and female depression scores. The p-value of 0.298 suggests that this difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, based on this data, there is no strong evidence to support a significant difference in depression levels between male and female university students. The t-value of -1.43 represents a relatively small difference in social anxiety scores between male and female students. However, the p-value of 0.154 suggests that this difference is not statistically significant at the conventional significance level. Therefore, based on this data, there is no strong evidence to conclude a significant difference in social anxiety levels between male and female university students. In this case, the t-value of 1.60 indicates a small difference in academic achievement scores between male and female students.

DISCUSSION

The findings of current study provide the distinction among male and woman college students in phrases of substance makes use of, melancholy, social anxiety and educational overall performance. Correlational

Research Design turned into used and facts turned into analyzed via way of means of SPSS. It turned into hypothesized that there may be dating among substance makes use of, melancholy, social tension and educational overall performance amongst university students. Findings via Pearson correlation on desk quantity three suggests that a huge difference among substance makes use of, melancholy, social tension amongst students. Results additionally indicates among substance makes use of and educational success among students. Results further indicate loneliness and social tension are bad huge correlated with educational success. Parent child association were found significant link with psychopathologies' (Jabeen & Akhtar.2024)The wonderful dating among substance use, melancholy, and social tension shows that accelerated substance use is related to better degrees of melancholy and social tension amongst students. Some students face social anxiety and use substance s as a method of self- remedy to briefly alleviate negative emotions or manipulate social fears (Blanco et al., 2008).

Substance use can contribute to extended symptoms and symptoms of despair and social anxiety It can create a cyclical pattern in which each difficulty reinforces the different. Increased substance use, together with drug or alcohol abuse, may have unfavourable consequences on substance use can impair cognitive functioning, attention, and memory, making it hard for students to concentrate, observe effectively, and carry out properly of their educational endeavours (Haug et al., 2004).

Depression is related to quite a number of signs that could affect educational achievement. Individuals experiencing melancholy can also additionally have low energy, problem concentrating, decreased motivation, and a loss of hobby in activities, consisting of educational pursuits. These elements can contribute to reduced productiveness and decrease educational overall performance. The worry and avoidance related to social tension can restrict possibilities for mastering and educational success (Nyer et al., 2015).

There have been no significant variations found among the genders in phrases in their tiers or reports associated with substance use, melancholy, social tension, and educational overall performance. These findings show that, on average, male and female students show off comparable styles and tiers in those variables. It suggests that gender isn't a sizable issue in explaining variations in those factors amongst students (Catley et al., 2012).

Research indicates that there isn't a significant distinction between male and female students in terms of substance use behaviours, including alcohol, drugs, or other substances (McCabe et al., 2007). Studies suggest that there isn't a significant difference in the prevalence or severity of depression between male and female students, indicating that both genders experience similar levels of depressive symptoms or susceptibility to depression (Cyranowski et al., 2000). It's observed that both male and female e students experience comparable levels of social anxiety, indicating similar degrees of discomfort or fear in social situations. Moreover, a hypothesis regarding the prediction of depression based on substance use among university students the results suggest that substance use moderately predicts depression among students. Approximately 15.6% of the variance in depression can be explained by substance use, indicating that substance use accounts for a notable portion of the variability in depression among university students.

LIMITATIONS

The study's limitations include a sample solely drawn from National Textile University Faisalabad and Government College University Faisalabad, limiting generalizability. Purposive sampling introduces selection bias, while participant self-selection may skew results. Correlational methodology prevents establishing causality, requiring longitudinal studies for temporal dynamics. Reliance on self-report introduces response bias and social desirability effects. Lack of control variables hampers understanding, and the study's context may not apply universally. Interpret findings cautiously, recognizing the need for further research to address these limitations and comprehensively understand the relationship between substance use, mental health, and academic performance among students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's choice of Faisalabad for data collection from university students suggests the potential benefit of expanding to include diverse institutions in different locations for future research.. Recommendations for future studies include random sampling for a more representative sample, broader age and demographic inclusion, and extending findings to both public and private educational institutions. Leveraging these findings, psychologists and researchers can develop intervention programs targeting substance use, depression, and social anxiety among college students, emphasizing prevention, awareness, and support services tailored to address these issues and promote mental well-being and academic success. Educational campaigns, inclusive interventions, and policy advocacy are vital for fostering a supportive campus culture and prioritizing student well-being and academic achievement.

REFERENCES

- Aafreen MM, Priya VV, Gayathri R. Effect of stress on academic performance of students in different streams. *Drug Invent Today*. (2018) 10:5.
- American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (5th ed.). American Psychiatric Association. 2013.
- American Psychiatric Association, D. S. M. T. F., & American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-5* (Vol. 5, No. 5). Washington, DC: American psychiatric association.
- Arkin, R. M., Lake, E. A., & Baumgardner, A. H. (1986). Shyness and self-presentation. *Shyness: Perspectives on research and treatment*, 189-203.
- Armstrong, T. D., & Costello, E. J. (2002). Community studies on adolescent substance use, abuse, or dependence and psychiatric comorbidity. *Journal of consulting and clinical psychology*, 70(6), 1224.
- Atherton, O. E., Conger, R. D., Ferrer, E., & Robins, R. W. (2016). Risk and protective factors for early substance use initiation: A longitudinal study of Mexican-Origin youth. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 26(4), 864-879.

- Blumenthal, H., Leen-Feldner, E. W., Frala, J. L., Badour, C. L., & Ham, L. S. (2010). Social anxiety and motives for alcohol use among adolescents. *Psychology of Addictive Behaviors, 24*(3), 529.
- Brown, B. B., Clasen, D. R., & Eicher, S. A. (1986). Perceptions of peer pressure, peer conformity dispositions, and self-reported behavior among adolescents. *Developmental psychology, 22*(4), 521.
- Bruch, M. A., Rivet, K. M., Heimberg, R. G., & Levin, M. A. (1997). Shyness, alcohol expectancies, and drinking behavior: Replication and extension of a suppressor effect. *Personality and Individual Differences, 22*(2), 193-200.
- Buckner, J. D., Mallott, M. A., Schmidt, N. B., & Taylor, J. (2006). Peer influence and gender differences in problematic cannabis use among individuals with social anxiety. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders, 20*(8), 1087-1102.
- Compas, B. E., Connor-Smith, J. K., Saltzman, H., Thomsen, A. H., & Wadsworth, M. E. (2001). Coping with stress during childhood and adolescence: Problems, progress, and potential in theory and research. *Psychological Bulletin, 127*(1), 87–127.
- Eggleston, A. M., Woolaway-Bickel, K., & Schmidt, N. B. (2004). Social anxiety and alcohol use: Evaluation of the moderating and mediating effects of alcohol expectancies. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders, 18*(1), 33-49.
- Ennett, S. T., Bauman, K. E., Hussong, A., Faris, R., Foshee, V. A., Cai, L., & DuRant, R. H. (2006). The peer context of adolescent substance use: Findings from social network analysis. *Journal of research on adolescence, 16*(2), 159-186.
- Essau, C. A., Conradt, J., & Petermann, F. (1999). Frequency and comorbidity of social phobia and social fears in adolescents. *Behaviour research and therapy, 37*(9), 831-843.
- Fite, P. J., Colder, C. R., & O'Connor, R. M. (2006). Childhood behavior problems and peer selection and socialization: Risk for adolescent alcohol use. *Addictive Behaviors, 31*(8), 1454-1459.
- Grant, B. F., & Dawson, D. A. (1997). Age at onset of alcohol use and its association with DSM-IV alcohol abuse and dependence: results from the National Longitudinal Alcohol Epidemiologic Survey. *Journal of substance abuse, 9*, 103-110.
- Griffin, A. M., Cleveland, H. H., Schlomer, G. L., Vandenberg, D. J., & Feinberg, M. E. (2015). Differential susceptibility: The genetic moderation of peer pressure on alcohol use. *Journal of youth and adolescence, 44*, 1841-1853.
- Ham, L. S., & Hope, D. A. (2005). Incorporating social anxiety into a model of college student problematic drinking. *Addictive behaviors, 30*(1), 127-150.
- Ham, L. S., Bonin, M., & Hope, D. A. (2007). The role of drinking motives in social anxiety and alcohol use. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders, 21*(8), 991-1003.
- Harter, S. (1988). Self-perception profile for adolescents. *Gifted Child Quarterly*.
- Heimberg, R. G., Brozovich, F. A., & Rapee, R. M. (2014). A cognitive-behavioral model of social anxiety disorder. *Social anxiety, 705-728*.

- Jabeen, S., Naz, J. & Akhtar, S. (2023). The influence of parenting styles on adolescents' mental health: a comprehensive study on intermittent explosive disorder, suicidality, and self-esteem. *PAKISTAN ISLAMICUS (An International Journal of Islamic & Social Sciences)*, 3(3), 594-603. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10702993>
- Likisa, K. D. (2018). Challenges and prospects of competency-based education: The case of adama science and technology university alumni students and hawas TVET college, adama, Ethiopia. *The Journal of Competency-Based Education*, 3(2), e01163.
- MacKinnon, D. P., Krull, J. L., & Lockwood, C. M. (2000). Equivalence of the mediation, confounding and suppression effect. *Prevention science*, 1, 173-181.
- McEwen, B. S. (2007). Physiology and neurobiology of stress and adaptation: central role of the brain. *Physiological reviews*, 87(3), 873-904.
- Merikangas, K. R., Avenevoli, S., Acharyya, S., Zhang, H., & Angst, J. (2002). The spectrum of social phobia in the Zurich cohort study of young adults. *Biological psychiatry*, 51(1), 81-91.
- Miers, A. C., Blöte, A. W., Bögels, S. M., & Westenberg, P. M. (2008). Interpretation bias and social anxiety in adolescents. *Journal of anxiety disorders*, 22(8), 1462-1471.
- Miers, A. C., Blöte, A. W., De Rooij, M., Bokhorst, C. L., & Westenberg, P. M. (2013). Trajectories of social anxiety during adolescence and relations with cognition, social competence, and temperament. *Journal of abnormal child psychology*, 41, 97-110.
- Morris, E. P., Stewart, S. H., & Ham, L. S. (2005). The relationship between social anxiety disorder and alcohol use disorders: A critical review. *Clinical psychology review*, 25(6), 734-760.
- Patton, G. C., Carlin, J. B., Coffey, C., Wolfe, R., Hibbert, M., & Bowes, G. (1998). Depression, anxiety, and smoking initiation: a prospective study over 3 years. *American journal of public health*, 88(10), 1518-1522.
- Rosenthal, J. M., & Okie, S. (2005). White coat, mood indigo-depression in medical school. *New England journal of medicine*, 353(11), 1085.
- Rucker, D. D., Preacher, K. J., Tormala, Z. L., & Petty, R. E. (2011). Mediation analysis in social psychology: Current practices and new recommendations. *Social and personality psychology compass*, 5(6), 359-371.
- SAMHSA. (2011). National survey on drug use and health.
- Schimelpfening, N. (2020). Causes and Risk Factors of Depression. *Hentet fra: https://www.verywellmind.com/common-causes-of-depression-1066772*.
- Skinner, H. A. (1982). *Drug use questionnaire (DAST-20)*. Addiction Research Foundation.
- Sher, K. J., & Levenson, R. W. (1982). Risk for alcoholism and individual differences in the stress-response-dampening effect of alcohol. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 91(5), 350.